

Categoria A

REVISTA ARHEOLOGICĂ

serie nouă _ vol. XVIII _ nr. 2

Indexată în bazele de date:

SCOPUS, ERIH PLUS, DOAJ, CEEOL, ROAD, ISIFI, CiteFactor

CHIȘINĂU 2022

ISSN 1857-016X
E-ISSN 2537-6144

INSTITUTUL PATRIMONIULUI CULTURAL
CENTRUL DE ARHEOLOGIE

REVISTA ARHEOLOGICĂ

Reesponsabil de volum/responsible for volume: dr. Ghenadie Sîrbu

Secretar de redacție/editorial secretary: Livia Sîrbu

Colegiul de redacție/Editorial Board

Dr. hab. **Igor Bruiako** (*Odesa*), dr. **Ludmila Bacumenco-Pîrnău** (*Chișinău*), dr. hab. **Dumitru Boghian** (*Târgu Frumos*), dr. **Roman Croitor** (*Aix-en-Provence*), dr. hab. **Valentin Dergaciov** (*Chișinău*), dr. **Alexandr Diachenko** (*Kiev*), dr. **Vasile Diaconu** (*Târgu Neamț*), dr. **Mariana Gugeanu** (*Iași*), prof. dr. hab. **Svend Hansen** (*Berlin*), prof. dr. hab. **Elke Kaiser** (*Berlin*), dr. **Maia Kașuba** (*Sankt Petersburg*), dr. **Sergiu Matveev** (*Chișinău*), prof. dr. hab. **Michael Meyer** (*Berlin*), dr. **Octavian Munteanu** (*Chișinău*), prof. dr. **Eugen Nicolae** (*București*), prof. dr. hab. **Gheorghe Postică** (*Chișinău*), dr. hab. **Eugen Sava** (*Chișinău*), dr. hab. **Sergei Skoryi** (*Kiev*), prof. dr. **Victor Spinei**, membru al Academiei Române (*București, Iași*), prof. dr. **Marzena Szmyt** (*Poznan*), dr. **Nicolai Telnov** (*Chișinău*), dr. hab. **Petr Tolochko**, membru al Academiei Naționale de Științe a Ucrainei (*Kiev*), dr. **Vlad Vornic** (*Chișinău*), dr. **Aurel Zanoci** (*Chișinău*).

Manuscrisele, cărțile și revistele pentru schimb, precum și orice alte materiale se vor trimite pe adresa: Colegiul de redacție al „Revistei Arheologice”, Centrul de Arheologie, Institutul Patrimoniului Cultural, bd. Ștefan cel Mare și Sfânt 1, MD-2001, Chișinău, Republica Moldova

Рукописи, книги и журналы для обмена, а также другие материалы необходимо посылать по адресу: редакция «Археологического Журнала», Центр археологии, Институт культурного наследия, бул. Штефан чел Маре ши Сфынт 1, MD-2001 Кишинэу, Республика Молдова

Manuscripts, books and reviews for exchange, as well as other papers are to be sent to the editorship of the “Archaeological Magazine”, Archaeology Centre, Institute of Cultural Heritage, 1 Ștefan cel Mare si Sfânt bd., MD-2001 Chisinau, Republic of Moldova

Toate lucrările publicate în revistă sunt recenzate de specialiști în domeniu după modelul *double blind peer-review*

Все опубликованные материалы рецензируются специалистами по модели *double blind peer-review*

All the papers to be published will be reviewed by experts according the *double blind peer-review* model

© IPC, 2022

CUPRINS – СОДЕРЖАНИЕ – CONTENTS

STUDII – ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ – RESEARCHES

Valery Manko (<i>Kiev</i>), Guram Chkhatarashvili (<i>Batumi</i>) Kvirike: The Early Holocene Site in Western Georgia	5
Kyrylo Gorbenko, Oleksandr Trygub (<i>Mykolaiv</i>) History of Exploration of Final Bronze Age Fortified Settlement (Hillfort) 'Dykyi Sad' (Mykolaiv, Ukraine)	17
Николай Николаев, Лилия Цыганенко (<i>Измаил</i>) Судебное магическое заклятие из Ольвии с «подписью автора»	35
Людмила Носова, Игорь Бруяко (<i>Одесса</i>) Римский период в истории археологического памятника у с. Орловка по данным нумизматики (монетные находки 2017-2018 гг.)	43
Сергей Скорый, Роман Зимовец (<i>Киев</i>), Алексей Орлик (<i>Кропивницкий</i>) Об «умерщвлении» предметов на тризне скифских курганов (по материалам Орликовой Могилы)	58

MATERIALE ŞI CERCETĂRI DE TEREN – МАТЕРИАЛЫ И ПОЛЕВЫЕ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ – PAPERS AND SURVEYS

Serghei Agulnikov (<i>Chişinău</i>) Complexe ale epocii bronzului târziu din situl Căplani I- <i>La Yurt</i> din nord-estul stepei Bugeacului	70
Natalia Mateevici (<i>Chişinău</i>), Nicolaie Alexandru, Robert Constantin, Mihai Ionescu (<i>Mangalia/Callatis</i>) Un lot nou de ştampile de amfore greceşti descoperite la Callatis	90

CERCETĂRI INTERDISCIPLINARE – МЕЖДИСЦИПЛИНАРНЫЕ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ – INTERDISCIPLINARY SURVEYS

Roman Croitor (<i>Chişinău/Aix-en-Provence</i>) Determination of the Paleolithic reindeer sex applying the K-means algorithm to frontal bones with pedicles	101
Lavinia Maria Brânduşan, Xenia Pop (<i>Satu Mare</i>) Studiu interdisciplinar efectuat asupra materialului ceramic şi arheozoologic provenit din situl nr.6 de pe varianta de ocolire a municipiului Satu Mare	107
Nicoleta Vornicu (<i>Iaşi</i>), Gheorghe Postică, Ludmila Bacumenco-Pîrnău (<i>Chişinău</i>), Cristina Bibire (<i>Iaşi</i>) Cercetarea mortarelor descoperite în situl medieval de la Orheiul Vechi prin metode nedestructive	124

RECENZII ŞI PREZENTĂRI DE CARTE – РЕЦЕНЗИИ И КНИЖНОЕ ОБОЗРЕНИЕ – PAPER AND BOOK REVIEW

Gheorghe Postică , <i>Aşezarea medievală timpurie de la Păhărniceeni – „Petruca” din Codrii Orheiului</i> , Editura Pontos, Chişinău, 2021, 163 p. ISBN 978-9975-72-602-3 (Ludmila Bacumenco-Pîrnău, <i>Chişinău/Iaşi</i>)	140
---	-----

LISTA ABREVIERILOR – СПИСОК СОКРАЩЕНИЙ – LIST OF ABBREVIATION	142
INFORMAȚII ȘI CONDIȚIILE DE EDITARE A <i>REVISTEI ARHEOLOGICE</i>	143
ИНФОРМАЦИЯ И УСЛОВИЯ ИЗДАНИЯ <i>АРХЕОЛОГИЧЕСКОГО ЖУРНАЛА</i>	144
INFORMATION AND CONDITION OF PUBLICATION IN THE <i>ARCHAEOLOGICAL MAGAZINE</i>	145

CERCETĂRI INTERDISCIPLINARE – МЕЖДИСЦИПЛИНАРНЫЕ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ – INTERDISCIPLINARY SURVEYS

Roman Croitor

Determination of the Paleolithic reindeer sex applying the K-means algorithm to frontal bones with pedicles

Key words: Late Paleolithic, Cosăuți, *Rangifer tarandus*, pedicles, sexual dimorphism, K-means clustering.

Cuvinte cheie: Paleoliticul superior, Cosăuți, *Rangifer tarandus*, pedicule, dimorfismul sexual, grupare K-means.

Mots clés: Paléolithique supérieur, Cosăuți, *Rangifer tarandus*, pédicules, dimorphisme sexuel, K-means clustering.

Roman Croitor

Determination of the Paleolithic reindeer sex applying the K-means algorithm to frontal bones with pedicles

The article presents the application of K-means clustering algorithm to sorting female and male pedicles of reindeer (*Rangifer tarandus*) from the Paleolithic site of Cosăuți from Soroca District (the Republic of Moldova). According to the obtained results, 29.8% of frontal bones with pedicles belong to males, while the rest of 70.2% of specimens belong to females. The obtained value of the sex ratio of the reindeer pedicle sample confirms the earlier study that obtained the same results based on sexual dimorphism of limb bones. The volume of pedicles represents the most secure parameter that allows to distinguish female pedicles from male pedicles. The distribution of pedicle volume size in the samples of males and females corresponds to the age profiles of the samples.

Roman Croitor

Determinarea sexului renului paleolitic prin aplicarea algoritmului K-means la oasele frontale cu pediculi

În articol este prezentată aplicarea algoritmului de grupare K-means la separarea pedicuilor de femele și masculi de ren (*Rangifer tarandus*) din situl paleolitic Cosăuți, raionul Soroca (Republica Moldova). Conform rezultatelor obținute, 29,8% din oasele frontale cu pediculi aparțin masculilor, în timp ce restul de exemplare (70,2%) aparțin femelelor. Valoarea obținută a raportului între sexe al seriei de pedicole de ren confirmă rezultatele studiilor anterioare care au obținut aceleași valori pe baza dimorfismului sexual al oaselor membrilor. Volumul pedicuilor reprezintă cel mai sigur parametru care permite distingerea pedicuilor feminini de pediculi masculini. Distribuția dimensiunii volumului pedicului în eșantioane de masculi și femele corespunde profilurilor de vârstă individuală ale eșantioanelor.

Roman Croitor

Détermination du sexe du renne paléolithique en appliquant l'algorithme K-means aux os frontaux à pédicules

L'article présente l'application de l'algorithme de K-means clustering au tri des pédicules de femelles et mâles de rennes (*Rangifer tarandus*) du site paléolithique de Cosăuți, district de Soroca (République de Moldavie). Selon les résultats obtenus, 29,8% des os frontaux avec pédicules appartiennent à des mâles, tandis que le reste de 70,2% des spécimens appartiennent à des femelles. La valeur obtenue du sex-ratio de l'échantillon étudié confirme les résultats d'études antérieures qui ont obtenu les mêmes ratios basés sur le dimorphisme sexuel des os des membres. Le volume des pédicules représente le paramètre le plus sûr permettant de distinguer les pédicules femelles des pédicules mâles. La distribution de la taille du volume pédiculaire dans les échantillons mâles et femelles correspond aux profils d'âge des échantillons.

Introduction

Reindeer represent an exceptional case among Cervidae because of the presence of antlers in both sexes [Lydekker 1878; Bubenik 1990]. The development of antlers in reindeer females is regarded as a peculiar adaptation in the conditions of tundra with a long-lasting snow cov-

er. Thus reindeer have to spend a considerable amount of time and energy while diffing the snow pits to gather their forage. The digging through snow is energetically costly, therefore the aggressive intraspecific kleptoparasitism is not unusual among reindeer [Tarasov 1956]. Therefore, according to Tarasov [1956], the development of an-

thers in reindeer females is an adaptation against intraspecific kleptoparasitism that allow females to defend their forage snow pits. Antlers of reindeer females are simpler and generally smaller. However, distinguishing male and female antler remains from Paleolithic sites is a real challenge because of ontogenetic and individual variations. The individual variation of reindeer antlers may depend on multiple factors, such as the health state, environmental conditions, and forage availability, therefore the sorting of reindeer male and female antlers from Paleolithic sites becomes an insurmountable task. Cervid antlers are attached to pedicles (*processus cornu cervi*), specific outgrowths of the frontal bones that are characteristic of the family Cervidae [Bubenik 1990]. Antlers are annually shed and regenerated apices of pedicles. Pedicles are influenced by strong ontogenetic variation that is correlated with the individual age of the animal. In juvenile individuals, pedicles are thin and long, while in older individuals antlers become short and more robust, corresponding to the size of fully grown antlers. Pedicles of reindeer females are comparatively smaller, however, the measurements of the pedicles of old females broadly overlap with the pedicle measurements of younger males [Bouchud 1966]. For this reason, remains of reindeer frontal bones from the Paleolithic sites were never considered in the description of the demographic structure of reindeer remains from the Palaeolithic sites [Bouchud 1966; Weinstock 2000, 2002; Croitor 2018].

The multilayered Paleolithic site of Cosăuți (Soroca District, the Republic of Moldova) placed by radiocarbon dating in the period from 20000 to 16000 years BP, has yielded a rich collection of artefacts made of bone, antler, and ivory material [Covalenco, Croitor 2016]. The most of artefacts (handles, sleeves, hammer-like tools, anvils, axe, adzes, picks, hoes, needles, awls, tubular cases for needles, and polishers) are characteristic of the “kill sites” of reindeer hunters [Covalenco, Croitor 2021]. The hunting took place in the autumn, during the seasonal migrations of reindeer.

The rich sample of reindeer remains from Cosăuți belongs to 188 individuals of different ages [David et al. 2003] that is characterized by a “catastrophic” demographic profile due to the specific ambush hunting practised by the Paleolithic hunters from Cosăuți [Croitor 2018]. The sex ratio

shown by different skeletal parts is similar, confirming the assumption that the entire killed reindeer were brought to the butchering site [Croitor 2018]. The demographic structure of the reindeer remains from Cosăuți indicates that the hunting strategy did not have any selective character. About three-quarters of the whole sample of the reindeer bones from Cosăuți belong to females, a ratio that is very close to the demographic structure of the modern tundra reindeer herd during seasonal migrations [Croitor 2018]. Therefore, the demographic profile of the reindeer sample from Cosăuți suggests that the hunters slaughtered the whole herd crossing the Dniester [Covalenco, Croitor 2022]. The particular character of the Cosăuți site function (specialized in the hunting of the migrating reindeer herds) and the hunting weapon assemblage permitted to classify of this archaeological monument as a “reindeer hunting camp” specific for the Late Upper Palaeolithic of the Middle Dniester [Covalenco, Croitor 2022].

The demographic structure of the reindeer sample from Cosăuți was established based on limb bone sexual dimorphism and fusion of long bone epiphyses that allow distinguishing adults from juveniles [Croitor 2018 and references therein]. The present paper proposes the K-means clustering algorithm as an effective tool permitting to distinguishing of females and males of reindeer based on frontal bones with pedicles. The well-studied archaeozoological material of reindeer from Cosăuți is very suitable for the K-means clustering test due to the relatively large size of the sample and the presence of pedicles of all ontogenetic stages of both sexes.

Research Methods and Material

The studied cranial material from the Paleolithic site of Cosăuți is highly fragmented. The pedicles (47 specimens) in most cases are attached to their pedicles. The reindeer remains from Cosăuți are stored in the paleontological collection of the Institute of Zoology (Chișinău, The Republic of Moldova). The measurements of pedicles considered in the present study: DAP, the anteroposterior diameter of the pedicle; DLM, the lateromedial diameter of the pedicle; H, the height of the pedicle measured at the posterolateral side from the frontoparietal suture to the upper edge of the pedicle. The volume of pedicles (V , mm³)

is another parameter considered in the analysis. It was calculated as the volume of a cylinder. The data are treated with the application of the K-means algorithm in Jupyter Notebook (Anaconda3) using Python-3 programming language.

Results

The K-means algorithm revealed the presence of two unequal-sized clusters of pedicles (Fig. 1). Both clusters include pedicles of all age groups from long thin pedicles of juvenile individuals to relatively robust and short pedicles of old individuals. The small cluster (29.8% of the sample) includes the largest pedicles of the sample and therefore is regarded here as a cluster that contains the pedicles of males. The large cluster (70.2% of the sample) contains comparatively smaller pedicles and is regarded here as a cluster that contains the cranial fragments of females (Tab. 1, Fig. 2). Measurements of pedicles from both clusters broadly overlap. The volume of pedicles is the character that distinguished those two clusters from one another better than simple measurements (Fig. 3).

Discussion and conclusions

The revealed ratio of male and female pedicles (Fig. 2) corresponds to the male/female ratio (24% versus 76%) based on the postcranial material of reindeer from Cosăuți and is very close to the sex ratio in a migrating herd of modern reindeer [Croitor 2018], thus confirming the hypothesis of non-selective ambush hunting strategy used

Fig. 1. Scatter diagram of measurements of reindeer male and female pedicles from Cosăuți.

Fig. 2. Sex ratio of reindeer from Cosăuți based on pedicles sorted by the K-means clustering algorithm.

Fig. 3. Comparison of pedicle volume of reindeer males and females from Cosăuți.

Fig. 4. Distribution of pedicle volume among reindeer females and males from Cosăuți.

by Paleolithic hunters.

The distribution of pedicle size within clusters is interesting and certainly reflects the age profile of males and females in the arbitrary reindeer herd from Cosăuți. The Kernel Distribution Estimation in figure 4 shows a very different distribution of male and female pedicle volume that corresponds to the animal's age. The character of

DAP	DLM	H	V	sex
20.8	18.5	24.5	3027.5	♂
22.2	21.1	20.5	2789.1	♂
22.6	21.7	21.0	2922.9	♂
23.0	21.0	20.2	2793.7	♂
23.6	22.0	19.5	2794.4	♂
23.7	20.7	19.0	2653.3	♂
23.8	22.8	19.0	2781.9	♂
27.6	24.5	16.1	2637.5	♂
28.0	25.3	21.0	3518.6	♂
29.3	24.3	21.5	3628.3	♂
30.8	27.0	19.0	3453.8	♂
32.7	30.1	20.0	3947.5	♂
36.0	30.0	13.5	2804.9	♂
40.9	39.0	14.8	3715.5	♂
14.2	12.8	22.5	1909.8	♀
17.1	14.0	18.5	1812.0	♀
18.2	16.2	11.1	1200.6	♀
18.3	17.0	16.0	1775.0	♀
19.0	15.9	12.4	1362.2	♀
19.1	17.7	19.3	2232.1	♀
19.1	18.0	14.0	1632.1	♀
19.4	17.4	15.0	1735.4	♀
20.5	18.5	11.0	1348.6	♀
20.5	18.3	14.5	1768.9	♀
20.6	18.5	14.0	1720.9	♀
20.6	20.1	16.0	2045.9	♀
20.8	18.0	19.5	2380.0	♀
21.0	18.3	15.4	1903.6	♀
21.0	18.9	18.0	2257.9	♀
21.2	18.3	15.9	1975.7	♀
22.0	17.9	14.0	1759.5	♀
22.0	20.8	16.0	2151.8	♀
22.0	22.0	15.5	2142.6	♀
22.4	19.0	17.3	2253.9	♀
22.5	22.0	15.0	2097.1	♀
22.7	18.5	16.4	2128.2	♀
22.7	20.0	9.0	1208.5	♀
22.9	20.0	15.0	2023.9	♀
23.7	22.2	15.0	2163.6	♀
24.1	21.6	14.5	2083.3	♀
24.5	21.8	10.5	1528.6	♀

25.4	24.4	11.1	1736.8	♀
26.4	26.1	12.3	2028.7	♀
26.5	22.3	11.1	1704.9	♀
27.0	24.3	14.0	2257.9	♀
28.5	26.5	12.5	2160.6	♀
28.8	25.0	12.0	2030.7	♀

Table 1. Measurements (mm) and calculated volume (mm³) of reindeer male and female pedicles from Cosăuți sorted by the K-means clustering algorithm.

distribution of pedicle volume of males and females from Cosăuți suggests its certain relationship to male and female mortality described by Reimers [1983] for Svalbard reindeer. According to Reimers [1982], the female mortality rate increased in the age interval of 2-4 years. Possibly, this juvenile female mortality is mirrored by the deepening on the left slope of the distribution of female pedicle size (Fig. 4). The male mortality rate in modern Swabard reindeer increases sharply in the age interval above 6 years [Reimers, 1982]. This high rare mortality of adult reindeer males corresponds to the comparatively low peak of male pedicle volume distribution and the right slope of the plot (Fig. 4). Reimers [1982] explains

the increasing mortality rate among adult reindeer males to their increased involvement in rutting activities associated with lower grazing activity and depletion of fat reserves.

The present study demonstrated that the implication of K-means clustering in the sorting of reindeer male and female pedicles gave adequate results that correspond to the male/female ratio obtained from the sexual dimorphism of postcranial bones. The pedicle volume is regarded here as the most suitable character distinguishing male and female pedicles in all age groups. The distribution of pedicle volume within male and female samples reflects the general age profile of males and females in a given sample.

Bibliography

- Bouchud 1966:** J. Bouchud, Essai sur le renne et la climatologie du Paléolithique moyen et supérieur (Périgueux 1966), 1-297.
- Bubenik 1990:** A.B. Bubenik, Epigenetical, morphological, physiological, and behavioral aspects of evolution of horns, pronghorns, and antlers. In: G.A. Bubenik, A.B. Bubenik (editors), Horns, pronghorns, and antlers (New York 1990), 3-113.
- Covalenco, Croitor 2016:** S. Covalenco, R. Croitor, Proizvodstvennyi i khiziaistvennyi inventar' iz kosti, roga i bivnia s mnogoslinoi stoiianki Koseuts'. Revista Arheologică, 12 (1-2), 2016, 283-295. // С. Коваленко, Р. Кроитор, Производственный и хозяйственный инвентарь из кости, рога и бивня с многослойной стоянки верхнего палеолита Косэуць. Revista Arheologică, 12 (1-2), 2016, 283-295.
- Covalenco, Croitor 2021:** S. Covalenco, R. Croitor, Palaeolithic reindeer hunting camps from Cosăuți (Middle Dniester, Moldova). Materiale și cercetări arheologice, 1 (1), 2021, 351-359.
- Croitor 2018:** R. Croitor, Paleobiology as a clue to Paleolithic taphonomy: the case of reindeer hunting in Moldova. Quaternaire, 29 (1), 2018, 81-86.
- David et al. 2003:** A. David, A. Nadachowski, V. Pascaru, P. Wojtal, I. Borziac, Late Pleistocene mammal fauna from the Late Palaeolithic butchering site Cosăuți 1, Moldova. Acta zoologica cracoviensia, 46 (1), 2003, 85-96.
- Reimers 1983:** E. Reimers, Mortality in Svalbard reindeer. Ecography, 6 (2), 1983, 141-149.
- Tarasov 1956:** P.P. Tarasov, O nekotorykh ocobennostiakh morfologii severnogo olenia kak zivotnogo tundry. Trudy Moskovskogo obshchestva ispytatelei prirody (novaia seriia), otdel biologicheskii, 61 (4), 1956, 80-82 // П.П. Тарасов, О некоторых особенностях морфологии северного оленя как животного тундры. Труды Московского общества испытателей природы (новая серия), отдел биологический, 61 (4), 1956, 80-82.
- Weinstock 2000:** J. Weinstock, Osteometry as a source of refined demographic information: sex-ratios of reindeer, hunting strategies, and herd control in the Late Glacial site of Stellmoor, Northern Germany. Journal of archaeo-

logical science, 27 (12), 2000, 1187-1195.

Weinstock 2002: J. Weinstock, Reindeer hunting in the Upper Palaeolithic: sex ratios as a reflection of different procurement strategies. *Journal of archaeological science*, 29 (4), 2002, 365-377.

Roman Croitor, PhD in Biology, Senior Scientific Researcher in the Institute of Zoology, Academiei 1 str., MD-2028, Chişinău, the Republic of Moldova; associated researcher of the Université Aix-Marseille, CNRS, UMR 7269, Maison méditerranéenne des sciences de l'homme, BP674, 5 Rue Château de l'Horloge, 13090 Aix-en-Provence, France; e-mail: romancroitor@europe.com, roman.croitor@zoology.md